

AMALIY VA FUNDAMENTAL TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI

Jild: 03 Nashr: 08 (2024)

www.mudarrisziyo.uz

The Role of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization in Uzbekistan and China's Relationship: Responsibility and Opportunity

Abdullayeva Ozoda

A leading specialist in the Department of quality control of Education at the University of world economy and diplomacy

Abstract: This article explores the critical role of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) in shaping and analyzing the bilateral relations between Uzbekistan and China. As a regional multilateral platform, the SCO has significantly influenced the dynamics of cooperation between these two nations, particularly in the realms of security, economic collaboration, and political dialogue. The organization provides a framework for addressing common security challenges, fostering economic partnerships through initiatives like the Belt and Road, and facilitating political coordination on regional and global issues. Additionally, the SCO enhances cultural exchanges and contributes to regional stability, which are vital to the evolving relationship between Uzbekistan and China. This article highlights the SCO's multifaceted impact, underscoring its importance as a cornerstone in the strategic partnership between these two countries.

Keywords: Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO), Uzbekistan, China, public diplomacy, "One belt, One road" project, multilateral diplomacy.

The Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) is recognized for its problem-solving capabilities, particularly in the areas of security and sustainable development. Its contributions to these fields have been significant. The Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) is an international institution that is widely respected. It was established in 1996-1997 and is relatively young compared to other historical institutions¹. The SCO is recognized as a prestigious and influential international structure. The Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) was initially formed as a group of five nations. Uzbekistan became a member of the organization in 2001². The primary objective of the SCO is to foster mutual friendship,

¹ The Shanghai Cooperation Organization was founded on June 15, 2001 in Shanghai on the basis of Declaration on the creation of the SCO, signed by Uzbekistan, China, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Russia and Tajikistan, as a permanent regional international organization. In 2017, the composition India and Pakistan were accepted as full members of the SCO.

² Declaration on the creation of the SCO. 06/15/2001 SCO website: www.sectsc.org (12/18/2021).

trust, and good neighborliness among its member states. In order to foster productive collaboration, it is crucial to enhance the conditions and concentrate on key areas such as politics, trade and economy, science and technology, culture, security, energy, transportation, tourism, and environmental conservation.

In June 2001, Independent Uzbekistan became a member of the “Shanghai Five”, an international organization that later evolved into the “Shanghai Cooperation Organization”.

The organization’s primary objective is to establish comprehensive relations between member states and to combat international terrorism and extremism, which has become the center of its activity. Over the past 20 years, the regional and international situation has been subject to ongoing changes.

However, the SCO has demonstrated its effectiveness as a mechanism for multilateral cooperation. In a short period of time, the organization has acquired a substantial contractual and legal basis, formed a complete institutional structure, established several structural bodies, and launched stable activities. Today, the SCO is committed to ensuring regional security and combating terrorism.

One of the main tasks of the organization is to address extremism, separatism, and the illegal drug trade. The headquarters for the fight against terrorism has been relocated from Bishkek to Tashkent. The specific tasks of the organization will be determined through discussions in the councils of the ministries of foreign affairs and defense³.

In recent years, Uzbekistan has proposed several initiatives to establish new cooperation platforms within the SCO. For instance, the SCO Public Diplomacy Center in Tashkent was opened by presidential decree. At the meeting of the SCO states in Astana on June 9, 2017, opinions were exchanged on various issues related to economic, cultural, and educational life, and general conclusions were drawn. During the summit, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, suggested that the leaders of SCO member states could benefit from enhancing cultural cooperation and utilizing public diplomacy mechanisms. As a result, the People’s Diplomacy Center of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization was established in Tashkent in 2018. The establishment of the Center of Public Diplomacy, as suggested by the President of Uzbekistan, is pertinent given the present global instability and growing threats. The establishment of the Center of Public Diplomacy, as suggested by the President of Uzbekistan, is pertinent given the present global instability and growing threats. The Center’s initiatives in Tashkent foster collaboration among SCO nations.

This statement aims to broaden opportunities, foster mutual trust, friendship, and good neighborliness, promote interethnic and interconfessional harmony, and enhance cooperation between civil society institutions and mass media.

On 15-16 September 2022⁴, the city of Samarkand hosted the 22nd summit of the SCO. Samarkand, located in the heart of the Great Silk Road, has been a center of international communication, cultural and spiritual cooperation, trade, and scientific exchanges for thousands of years. The SCO summit held in Samarkand is significant because it brought together the leaders of 14 Eurasian countries, including Pakistan, Iran, India, Russia, Turkey, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, China, Turkmenistan, Tajikistan, Belarus, and Mongolia. Despite the challenges posed by the pandemic and the complex global situation, this achievement can be considered a major success for Uzbek diplomacy in establishing itself as a center of international politics and economy.

³ On information records of the Regional Anti-Terrorist Structure. RATS SCO website://ecrats.org/ru/news/6914 (03/16/2021).

⁴ Official website of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan://president.uz/ru/lists/view/5495 (12.09.2022).

During the presidency of the SCO, Uzbekistan aimed to enhance practical cooperation within the organization, increase its potential, and boost its international prestige. Priority attention was given to expanding trade, economic, and humanitarian cooperation, in addition to security issues.

Numerous initiatives were implemented across all areas of the organization's activities. Despite the impact of the pandemic and the global crisis, over 80 major events were successfully held. During this period, Uzbekistan took a number of measures that resulted in the signing of over 40 documents, which is the highest number in the history of the organization⁵.

Proposals of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan at the Samarkand Summit of the SCO

№	Fields	Suggestions
1	Economy	<p><i>A common space of industrial and technological cooperation based on the start of a new economic dialogue of the SCO formation</i></p> <p><i>Conducting business partnership week of SCO regions in Uzbekistan</i></p> <p><i>Creation of an alliance of special economic zones of the SCO countries</i></p> <p><i>The first of the heads of administrations of special zones at the base of the “Uzbekistan-SCO” industrial zone in Samarkand holding a meeting</i></p> <p><i>holding a large SCO trade fair every year, creating a single electronic platform based on it</i></p>
2	Transportation	<p><i>Support for the construction of the Termiz - Mazari-Sharif - Kabul - Peshawar railway</i></p> <p><i>Establishment of a joint special fund for humanitarian support to Afghanistan in the city of Termiz - using the modern infrastructure of the existing transport and logistics situation there</i></p> <p><i>Establishment of Interregional Interdependence Center in Tashkent</i></p> <p><i>the first SCO transport forum in Uzbekistan next year</i></p>
3	Ecology	<p><i>politicians, public figures, scientists and environmental experts,</i></p> <p><i>creation of the SCO Climate Council, which can unite business representatives</i></p>
4	Security	<p><i>Establishing the practice of annual traveling meetings of the regional anti-terrorist structure council</i></p>

⁵“Халқ сўзи” газетаси, 18 сентябр 2022 йил.

5	Culture, sports and tourism	<i>establishment of additional formats such as days of culture and tourism, joint sports events and universiades; declaration of 2023 as the “Year of Tourism Development in the SCO Area”</i>
---	------------------------------------	--

In summary, the geopolitical changes and breakdown of the previous security system, along with the stability that emerged at the end of the 20th century, the active development of globalization processes, and the formation of independent states in the post-Soviet region, have necessitated new forms of multilateral cooperation, both regionally and globally.

Uzbekistan co-founded the CIS and the SCO, demonstrating its commitment to strengthening security, stability, and sustainable development in the Central Asian region. As an active participant in these organizations, Uzbekistan is well-positioned to lead efforts towards achieving these goals. Uzbekistan's participation in the activities of the CIS and the SCO is a crucial aspect of the republic's foreign policy. Effective multidisciplinary cooperation is essential in the modern world to ensure peace, stability, and sustainable development in the region. The republic is committed to promoting international and regional security among member countries of these organizations, fostering mutually beneficial economic relations and industrial cooperation, and enhancing constructive collaboration in high-tech and innovative development, transport and transit, education, and other areas of partnership. We prioritize science, tourism, health, and other fields.

To adapt the CIS and SCO to modern political and economic reality, it is crucial to maintain a reasonable balance of national and regional interests, as well as the principles of consistent implementation of decisions made by all member countries within the framework of these associations. This is the basis for trust and mutual benefit, which are essential for their effective operation.

REFERENCES

1. Алимов Р. ШОС: становление, развитие, перспективы. – Москва: Издательство “Весь мир”, 2017.
2. Aris, S. 2009. The Shanghai Cooperation Organisation: Tackling the Three Evils. A Regional Response to Non-Traditional Security Challenges or an Anti-Western Bloc? *Europe-Asia Studies*, 61 (3).
3. Кушкумбаев С. Роль ШОС в противодействии вызовам и угрозам безопасности в Центральной Азии // Материалы двенадцатого заседания форума ШОС. – Ташкент: ИСМИ, 2018.
4. Клещева Т. Шанхайская организация сотрудничества как основной орган борьбы с терроризмом в странах АТР // *Право и политика*. – 2012, №1.
5. Porshneva O., Rakhimov M., Razinkov S. Historical and Legal Aspects of the SCO Formation and Institutional Development in Shanghai Cooperation Organization: From Interaction to Integration exploring New Horizons. Edited by Sergey Marochkin and Yury Bezborodov. Routledge 2022. P. 9-24.
6. Рахимов С. Торгово-экономическое сотрудничество Узбекистана в рамках СНГ // *Демократизация и права человека*. – 2018, №1 (77).
7. Современные международные отношения и мировая политика: учебник // Отв. ред. – Член-корреспондент РАН, проф. А.В. Торкунов. – Москва: Просвещение, 2004.

8. ШОС и проблемы безопасности Евразии / Под ред. Розанова А.А. // Совместное исследование Женевского центра по демократическому контролю над вооруженными силами, Белорусского государственного университета и КИСИ. – Минск/Алматы/Женева, 2012. – 194 с.
9. Shaw, M. International Law. Sixth edition. Cambridge University Press, 2008.
10. Song, W. 2014. Interests, Power and China's Difficult Game in the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO). Journal of Contemporary China, 23 (85), 85-101.